

Kurdistan Regional Government

Ministry of Education

A Research on

**English Language Teaching in Kurdistan: Methods, Challenges, and
Solutions from a Teacher-Centered Perspective"**

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Dedication

This study is dedicated to the **English Teachers of the Kurdistan Region**, who are teaching the future generations with commitment, hard work, and dignity. They encounter so many challenges during each academic year and yet they persevere and overcome them. The study is also dedicated to my friends and family for their support and belief in me. For everyone who is working to improve quality of education, this work is a tribute to all the efforts you put in.

Abstract

Globalization and the demand for communication skills have led the English language to become one of the demanded proficiencies in Kurdistan. This study attempts to explore the challenges and methodologies in **English Language Teaching (ELT) in Kurdistan** and emphasizes the perspectives of teachers. Based on a survey of **100 English teachers** from diverse educational institutions, the study focuses on teaching methods employed, serious challenges faced, and possible improvements in ELT. Results show that teachers frequently apply Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Learning (TBL), and the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), but they still face challenges including scarce teaching resources, large class sizes, low student motivation, and the English curriculum. The study also explored the teachers' views about the effectiveness of the present teaching resources and the inadequacy of training programs, innovative resources, and use of technologies. The results raise the question of government support for ELT in order to enhance teaching quality and student outcomes. Addressing these challenges through policy reform and concrete measures will be imperative in carving the future of English education in Kurdistan.

Keywords: English Language Teaching (ELT), Kurdistan, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), teacher training, curriculum challenges, technology integration.

Table of Contents

i. Acknowledgments	ii
ii. Dedication	iii
iii. Abstract	iv
1. Introduction	1
○ 1.1 Background of the Study	1
○ 1.2 Purpose and Objectives	1
○ 1.3 Research Questions	2
2. Literature Review	3
○ 2.1 Development of ELT in Iraq	3
○ 2.2 Global Approaches to ELT.....	3-4
○ 2.3 Historical Overview of ELT in Iraq.....	4
○ 2.4 ELT in the Kurdistan Region: A Critical Overview	5
○ 2.5 Current Trends in ELT	5
3. Research Methodology	6
○ 3.1 Research Design	6
○ 3.2 Population and Sampling	6
○ 3.3 Data Collection and Analysis	6
○ 3.4 Research Instrument.....	6
○ 3.5 Ethical Considerations	6
○ 3.6 Limitations of the Study	7
○ 3.7 Conclusion	7
4. Findings and Discussion	7
○ 4.1 Teaching Methods in Practice	7-11

○ 4.2 Challenges in ELT	12-15
○ 4.3 Evaluation of English Teaching Materials	15
○ 4.4 Policy Recommendations	16
5. Teacher-Driven Solutions and Recommendations for Improving ELT	16
○ 5.1 Enhancing Teacher Training	17
○ 5.2 Improving Teaching Materials and Curriculum	17
○ 5.3 Reducing Class Sizes and Improving Student-Teacher Ratios	18
○ 5.4 Integrating More Technology in Classrooms	18
○ 5.5 Expanding Opportunities for Speaking Practice	18
○ 5.6 Extending Lesson Duration or School Year	19
○ 5.7 Introducing More Extracurricular Activities	19
○ 5.8 Encouraging Real-World Learning Opportunities	19
○ 5.9 Promoting Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving	19
○ 5.10 Changing Teaching Approaches	20
6. Conclusion	21
7. References	22

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, English is considered an essential skill for academic, professional, and social advancement in a globalized world. It is taught as a foreign language in different educational settings, including public schools, private schools, universities, and language centers. Meanwhile, the effectiveness of English Language Teaching (ELT) remains a daunting challenge. Insufficient resources, old-fashioned curriculum, oversized classes, and poor teacher training are some of the important factors involved. The rapid pace of technology and innovations in teaching methodologies also need continual adjustment to improve the quality of ELT.

A lot has been done recently in the Kurdistan region to reform the educational system, especially in language teaching and learning. Nevertheless, there exists a huge gap between the desired level of English proficiency and what is being actually taught in classrooms through classroom practices and learning experiences. This study intends to investigate the current status of ELT practice in Kurdistan by focusing on the challenges faced by the teachers and the means they seek to overcome those challenges. The research aims to identify critical areas in ELT practice so as to contribute to the discussion on improving English language education in the region.

1.2 Purpose and Objectives

The aim of this study is to examine English Language Teaching's present condition in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq. The objectives of this research include finding out the challenges faced by English teachers, assessing the effectiveness of teaching methods, and suggesting ways and opportunities for improvement. Furthermore, through the study's assessment of teachers' experiences and perceptions, an overview of the strengths and weaknesses of ELT in the region will emerge.

The study aims to:

- To investigate the teaching methods applied within English Language Teaching in the Kurdistan region.
- To identify the challenges faced by English teachers, including but not limited to resources, student motivation, size of classes, and curriculum design.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of teaching materials and the use of technology in the ELT process.
- To get suggestions from teachers on how ELT practices may improve in the Kurdistan Region.

1.3 Research Questions

This research will investigate the following queries:

1. Which are the most prominent methods of English language teaching in Kurdistan? How do these methods, equip available resources and technological tools impact students' proficiency and motivation in the language?
2. What are the major challenges facing English teachers in this region regarding curriculum limitations, class size, heterogeneous student capabilities, and the difference between the intended curriculum and that used in practice in the classroom?
3. What are the perceptions of English teachers in Kurdistan regarding the current materials available for the teaching process, and what recommendations are there for improvement of the same in regard to resources, methods of instruction, and assessment?
4. What modifications are necessary in teacher training programs in Kurdistan for the provision of new teaching strategies, an effective classroom management technique, and technology in an educator's instruction?
5. What policy revisions including curriculum improvement, raising budget for educational resources and widening the scope of extracurricular opportunities lead to the enhancement of ELT and increase in student engagement, as well as actual language mastery in Kurdistan?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Development of ELT in Iraq

The historical factors and influences, including certain external temptations, have formulated a lot of changes in the developments and evolvement of English Language Teaching (ELT) in Iraq with time. The arrival of English language into Iraq has been dated as early as the British mandate in the beginning of the 20th century. Today, the uses of the language become the heart of life, such as education, business, travelling, and any diplomatic activities. Unfortunately, despite the excellent services of ELT, many limits were encountered in political unrest, civil disorder, and conflict. According to Amin (2017), ELT teaching styles and reformations have gone with the flow of societal and even higher academic needs in different periods, although often barred by a persistent and resource-strained political environment.

2.2 Global Approaches to ELT

There are different strategies for teaching English worldwide, with distinct advantages and disadvantages with regard to each. Some of these most noted methods are as follows:

1. Grammar Translation Method (GTM): This method has been extensively followed for years in different parts of the world, with a great emphasis on direct instruction in grammar and vocabulary learning. Although it has been criticized for being obsolete due to limited concentration on communication skills, it is widely used in classrooms where language learning is seen as a formal academic field (Richards and Rodgers, 2014).

2. Communicative Language Teaching: This, however, develops the communication skills in a more practical, real-world context with an emphasis on speaking and listening. According to Richards and Rodgers (2014), we can say that CLT is a practical means of the promotion of language use in day-to-day circumstances. This will particularly be meaningful in an EFL environment like Kurdistan, where learners find it hard to transfer language abilities into practice in contexts outside the classroom.

3. In task-based learning (TBL): learning is encouraged when the students engage in practical problem-solving or communication-real task usage. The TBL, inspired by the constructivist principles of learning, promotes experiential learning and has been proved to have a positive effect on the learners' involvement and the achievement of the desired performance in the target language (Ellis, 2003).

4. Blended learning: combines face-to-face instruction with digital technologies to construct more flexible learning contexts. The approach is valuable especially at those places where availability differs, for it avails opportunities for online as well as offline learning (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004).

CLT and TBL were introduced to the Kurdistan Region as part of ongoing modernization of the language education system. However, the implementation is still very much in progress and faces a few practical problems to overcome before their full effectiveness can be achieved in local classrooms.

2.3 Historical Overview of ELT in Iraq

First few years, English forms part of the national public education in Iraq that does date back to 1873 during the British colonization. Language instruction had reference mostly to the Egyptian books as imported, which used the Grammar Translation Method. The interpretation of it was based on reading and writing-the speaking and pronunciation are of far less concern. Their memorization involves phrases and sentences to be performed, but the language itself was not engaged. It was later by the 1970s that the Iraqi Ministry of Education initiated modernization of English teaching by formulating the New English Course for Iraq (NECI). By 1980, there were about 22 of such texts using the Structural Approach and the so-called Audio-Lingual Method, an approach that had located heavy emphasis in replications alongside memorizing and correction by teachers whenever students make mistakes in class. Throughout the period termed late 1970s and early 1980s, however, one could observe a slow movement toward the Communicative Approach aiming to surpass the rigid linguistic drills in favor of real-life communication skills.

This was the transition that continued into the 21st century when, in 2001, the Rafidain English Course for Iraq (RECI) was introduced into the Ministry. The design of the course focused on the principles of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), in which RECI builds the communication capacity of the learners in many social contexts. CLT was already on its way to gaining worldwide popularity because of its emphasis on communicative competence in ensuring that learners acquire not only grammatically correct but also contextually appropriate English.

2.4 ELT in the Kurdistan Region: A Critical Overview

Iraqi Kurdistan followed the same English curriculum as the rest of the country until 2007 after political autonomy was achieved in 1991. The existing syllabi were based on outdated pedagogical approaches and did not support adequately the growth of strong communication skills among students (Ahmed, Puteh-Behak, & Sidek, 2015). Therefore, in 2007, the KRG announced the introduction of the new Sunrise curriculum as an attempt to provide a more effective method of English language teaching. The curriculum consists of twelve levels, each with a wide range of supporting resources available, including textbooks, activity books, teacher manuals, and audio materials. However, many teachers still claim that even with these changes, the curriculum has not really achieved its stated purposes, pointing out problems still confronting the English language education system in the region.

2.5 Current Trends in ELT

There has been a concerted national effort in the recent years to enforce all educational levels, particularly in improving English proficiencies. English learning now starts from early childhood and goes on into higher education; such efforts underscore the severity of a national commitment to making language skills so developed in line with global trends. The demand to the English language continues to grow globally so that the countries in the Middle East and Asia are called upon the recognition of it being learned as a foreign language. In Iraq, students having their background in both Kurdish and Arabic seem to give extra motivation in learning English considering it as the language of science, tourism, and social media. Above that, a number of students are, in fact, just yearning to be part of English-language literature and films as well as television, therefore realizing that the more English they speak, the better their employment opportunities and reaching their messages and business to the world will be.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a descriptive survey research design with a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative structured questionnaires and qualitative open-ended responses to analyze ELT challenges in Kurdistan.

3.2 Population and Sampling

The study surveyed **100 English language** teachers from public and private schools, universities, language centers, and online platforms in Kurdistan.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis

An online survey gathered demographic data, teaching methods, challenges, and recommendations. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage distributions, mean, and standard deviation), while thematic analysis identified key themes in qualitative responses.

Demographics of Participants

- **Gender:** 59% Female, 40% Male, 1% Prefer not to say
- **Age:** 63% (25-35), 17% (36-45), 3% (46+)
- **Institution Type:** 80% Public Schools, 16% Private Schools, 2% University, 1% Private Language Centers, 1% Online Platforms
- **Grade Levels Taught:** 26% (Grades 1-3), 51% (Grades 4-6), 39% (Grades 7-9), 20% (Grades 10-12)

3.4 Research Instrument

The questionnaire included sections on demographics, teaching methods, challenges, teaching materials, and recommendations for ELT improvement.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured, with informed consent obtained. Data was solely for research purposes.

3.6 Limitations of the Study

- Convenience sampling may limit the generalizability of the findings, as the sample may not represent all English teachers in Kurdistan.
- The self-reported nature of survey responses could introduce bias, as participants may overstate their use of preferred methodologies.
- The use of only survey data, without in-depth interviews or classroom observations, restricts the qualitative depth and contextual understanding of teacher practices.

3.7 Conclusion

This methodology ensures a structured approach to analyzing ELT in Kurdistan, offering insights to educators and policymakers for future improvements.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Teaching Approaches Adopted by Educators

The survey findings illustrate a shifting landscape in English language instruction across Kurdistan, where teachers integrate both conventional and modern methodologies to accommodate their students' needs. While some techniques remain deeply embedded in long-standing traditions, others signify a transition toward interactive and communicative teaching styles.

Grammar-Translation Method (GTM)

Its direct and emphasis on grammar instruction, vocabulary acquisition, and direct translation from English into the learners' native tongues characterize the Grammar-Translation Method (GTM). Nevertheless, despite evolution into multiple routes of methodology in language teaching, **57% of the teachers surveyed still prefer GTM**. For instructors, the method offers its advantages apart from any others since it fits well with standardizing testing or align the curriculum to the rigid frames it provides. On the flip side, it has severe disadvantages, such as its neglect of speaking and listening, which deprive students of developing spontaneous dialogues and discussions on topics in their own learned proficiency. GTM is still widely used, but its role in promoting skills useful for real communication is strongly debated.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

Almost 51% of teachers use Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in their classrooms, signifying a shift toward a method that is less teacher-centered and more learner-centered. Under a traditional setting for rote-learning and direct translation learning, CLT quickly becomes familiar with meaningful communication while acquiring language naturally by very much engaging students in activities of role-play, discussion, and group assignments where they try to use the language practically.

However, there stand some challenges with CLT; one is that it requires active participation of students; in cases where students are shy to speak, it will not be effective. Apart from this, the teachers would require a specialized training platform for them to recreate the communication-based lesson when implemented. Still, this has not been much supportive to bring full integration of CLT into classrooms.

Blended Learning (Digital and In-Class Instruction)

Currently, only **10% of teachers are using Blended Learning**, a teaching method that combines online and in-person instruction. In this setting, students can work through the digital material at their own pace and receive direct support from instructors. However, the actual implementation is limited because of different challenges, including uneven access to technology, varying levels of digital literacy among both teachers and students, and irregular internet service in some geographical regions.

Task-Based Learning (TBL)

To about 23 % of educators, Task-Based Learning would mean real-world application of language practice rather than focusing on hypothetical exercises. The TBL approach encourages students to really elicit the natural language found through meaningful exchanges and activities such as problem-solving tasks and participative discussions. It is capable of improving students' critical thinking but also an excellent describer of sustained language retention. Though it is well defined, the busy lesson planning and healthy environment - an atmosphere in which students do not hesitate to practice - are also of the essence for TBL.

Interactive and Visual-Based Techniques

In-depth analysis shows that a striking **56 % of teachers** believe in the use of interactive and visual techniques like word maps, concept maps, educational games, and KWL for designing lessons that are more interesting and better understood. This method promotes deeper learning and retention over time.

- **Mind Mapping and Concept Mapped** with visual organization of conceptual relations facilitate the idea of increased understanding by students.
- **Educational Games** add the sense of competition and fun in the classroom, which ultimately increases engagement among students.
- **KWL Strategies** help students take ownership of their education by setting objectives, keeping focus, and thinking about the progress they have made.

These techniques create in the mind of the teacher a dynamic learning environment where students learn to engage with the English language meaningfully and naturally.

Total Physical Response (TPR)

Only 1% of teachers reported using Total Physical Response (TPR), a method that integrates physical movement with language learning, making it particularly effective for younger or beginner learners. The low adoption rate suggests that most teachers favor other approaches better suited to older students or structured curricular expectations.

Traditional Curriculum-Based Approaches

Similarly, only 1% of educators adhere strictly to the classic methods outlined in the national curriculum.

Specialized and Niche Teaching Strategies

A small subset of teachers (1% each) employs distinctive instructional techniques, such as:

- **Foundational Literacy and Numeracy Methods**, designed to build essential reading and mathematical skills for young learners through structured exercises and engaging activities

6. What teaching methods do you primarily use? (Select all that apply)

100 responses

The study highlights a contradiction in teaching practices:

Using a legitimate curriculum-based approach like the current one for CLT in Kurdistan (the SR classes fit to be certified as CLT), a majority of the teachers (57%) have still remained as supporters of "grammar translation method". This clearly indicates a dissatisfaction between what methodologies are prescribed and what actually happens in classrooms. The factors may be the lack of training for teachers on CLT methods and some practical obstacles in applying communicative techniques with students who do not possess strong foundations, along with an evaluation system that favors grammar over communication. The answer to this problem demands a targeted professional development course on which teachers will receive training in developing confidence and skill in the application of communicative teaching. Measurement strategies should also be modified towards emphasizing communicative skills instead of rote grammatical memorization. Such would bring both convergence of practice toward objectives of the current language learning process and enhancement of the students' capability in using English within the context of real scenarios. Majority Shown have tremendous affinity towards interactive student-centered methods like games, technology, and task-based learning, but findings indicate the same hybrid model approach that combines both traditional and modern methodologies in Kurdistan. Much reliance on conventional methods still creates an urgent demand for further developing diversified and adaptable teaching strategies that can meet the changing demands of language learners in the 21st century.

Conclusion

Results seem to indicate that GTMs are still common, but there appears to be a growing trend towards communications-focused, interactive, and technology-rich teaching methods. Increased usage of CLT, Blended Learning, TBL, and visuals-based approaches indicates a change in the direction of English language teaching that intends to achieve student interaction and real-life language skills. Yet, barriers such as limited access to technology for the innovative approach, inadequate teacher training, and inflexible curriculum requirements may prevent full-scale adoption.

4.2 Challenges in English Language Teaching in Kurdistan

The issues that have been flagged in the research highlight that the English teachers of Kurdistan are in perilous conditions, which indeed points out toward some structural issues that influence effectiveness in ELT in terms of their requirements. These problems, therefore, make us aware of the areas that needed urgent improvement so that educational standards are enhanced, wherein useful language skills may be ensured.

The most given argument for challenge according to **51% of respondents is too much material to be taught in a short period of time**. This means that the current curriculum lacks quality because such overloading doesn't give teachers much time for every credit hour to teach subject content well or even meaningfully engage students. Lessons become hurried, considering the many subjects one can cover in a short time; hence, understanding the subject for the students becomes very difficult. This idea creates a way of arguing about the need for curriculum revisions not only for coverage but for comprehension.

Moreover, **50% of the teachers reported that large class sizes were an important challenge**. Individual attention is increasingly difficult, as is conducting proper assessments of students and facilitating interactive learning activities-in fact, within overcrowded classrooms much less is possible. Overcrowded classes pose challenges in evaluating students thoroughly, engaging activities, and attending to all students with specific attention. An exceedingly large class size restricts possibilities for communicative practice, which is an important part of language acquisition. Instead of involving students in conversations, role-playing, or group projects-all essential for fostering real-world students in conversations, role-playing, or group projects-all of which are essential for building real-world language proficiency-teachers have successfully turned to lecture-based methods. Damage mitigation requires structural adjustments such as lowering a student-per-teacher ratio or putting in place classroom management strategies that optimize participation.

Moreover, 46% saw low English proficiency among pupils as a problem while another 46% of respondents said that they are very worried about pupils' lack of English competence. This difficulty has to do with a student's disinterested attitude and, therefore, it is seen as a very deep-seated contradiction between enlightenment goals and language learning capabilities actualized in a student. Most learners enter the classroom without basic knowledge and hence cannot meet the curricular requirements. Such problems have been connected with early exposure to English, not enough outside practice, and limited access to English materials. Thus, more time for remedial education has been consumed and taken from further enhancing students' abilities. The problem closely ties with another one: student motivation which has been identified by Ghafar and Amin (2022) and Dörnyei (2001) as one of the major challenges in ELT.

According to 41% of educators, lack of motivation among students is often cited and many students show little interest in learning English, which can be associated with either lack of real-life applications, monotonous teaching approaches, or cultural beliefs which belittle the importance of office. A shift towards more interactive, actively participating, and student-centered teaching approaches may bring back the interest in learning the target language.

Another issue is a dearth of teaching materials, which was mentioned by **37% of respondents.** **Without proper teaching materials** such as e-space, supplements and textbooks, a teacher's performance in the class would be limited. The absence of up-to-date textbooks, technological inputs, and so on prevents teachers from creating a dynamic and riveting educational environment.

In the same way, approximately **one-third of the teachers indicated technology as a limitation** which can huge number of schools cannot be said to be equipped with the needed infrastructure for digital learning and modern methods of teaching. With the absence of technology in their courses both teachers and students suffer, especially now that the teaching-learning process relies heavily on today's digital technology. Also, the essential resources like computers, projectors, and a good internet connection prevent schools from going into multimedia content online platforms and interactive learning methods. Improving access to technology and training teachers on how to use it impactfully will significantly boost the quality of education.

An issue regarding the curriculum was highlighted by 27 percent of teachers who reported that the current English curriculum was seen as being outdated or difficult to implement or unsuitable for students. Some teachers view the curriculum as outdated or disconnected from students' real-world needs and thus difficult to implement effectively this issue is also noted by Sofi-Karim (2015), who emphasizes on updating resources and curricula. A curriculum that relies too heavily on grammar drills and rote memorization rather than practical communicative skills will not adequately prepare students for real-life use of language. With this need for curriculum reform, increasingly more communicative and task-based learning would let students be linguistically competent and confident using English outside classrooms.

At the end the More-Practical Use of Language by 1% of the participants, which only a token few approved that there is a significant gap in the academic institution's curriculum on the practical enactment of real-life communication skills. Many graduates, although having learned English conceptually, find it quite difficult to apply this knowledge in various settings. This discrepancy indicates the need for a more effective shift from classroom instruction to real-life application, like task-based projects, simulation for interaction, and exposure to authentic English environments through various media and cultural interaction.

Thus, the urgency in reforming English language teaching (ELT) across Kurdistan is underscored. Improving English education calls for a joint effort by teachers, policymakers, and educational establishments to best confront these challenges. Curriculum interventions must emphasize an equilibrium between theoretical and practical knowledge to afford students comprehensive language training. Teacher-training programs need to incorporate recent trends in pedagogy and classroom management to prepare teachers for the mixed classes of students and

to create more participative learning environments. Increased investments in teaching resources and digital infrastructure are needed to enhance teachers' ability to teach the language.

At the same time, establishing a very dynamic and communicative atmosphere in class can tremendously boost student engagement and proficiency in the language. With effective reform and a cooperative approach, English language teaching in Kurdistan can develop into an even more impactful, interesting, and application-oriented system, thereby preparing students for academic and professional opportunities in the increasingly interconnected world.

4.3 Evaluation of English Teaching Materials in Kurdistan

The quality of English teaching materials is vital for effective ELT. Survey results show mixed opinions among teachers regarding the current materials:

- 51% were neutral, neither finding the materials effective nor ineffective.
- 24% rated them as effective.
- 9% considered them very effective.
- 9% found them ineffective.
- 7% rated them very ineffective.

These results indicate that many teachers are either uncertain or dissatisfied with the current materials, emphasizing the need for updates to the curriculum, textbooks, and better technology integration to better serve both teachers and students.

8. How would you rate the current English teaching materials used in Kurdistan?
100 responses

4.4 Policy Recommendations and the Need for Improvement in English Language Teaching in Kurdistan

One of the survey's key conclusions is the strong need for additional government funding for English language education. When asked whether the Ministry of Education should secure more funding for English language teaching (ELT), **a massive 97% of the respondents said yes**, which shows a general agreement on extra government investment. **Only 3% said "no,"** thus suggesting that they consider the existing investment to be appropriate.

This may call for policy changes and financing to strengthen the sector, given that challenges include insufficient resources, obsolete curricula, and a necessity for teacher training programs. Teachers largely agree that increased investment would lead to better quality and outcomes in ELT for Kurdistan. Furthermore, most of the English language teachers in Kurdistan believe that ELT demands enormous improvements. The results of the survey show:

- 93% think improvement is needed.
- 5% say there is no need for improvement.
- 2% are not sure.

9. Do you think English teaching in Kurdistan needs improvement?
100 responses

Implications of These Findings

The 93% advocating for improvements indicates widespread recognition of gaps in the current system, including insufficient resources, large class sizes, and lack of technology integration. The 5% who see no need for change may work in better-equipped institutions. Overall, these findings point to an urgent need for reform in teacher training, curriculum development, and resource allocation.

5. Teacher-Driven Solutions and Recommendations for Improving ELT in Kurdistan

Drawing from survey results and educator feedback, several critical areas have been identified to strengthen English language teaching (ELT) in Kurdistan. The following key recommendations have been prioritized:

5.1 Enhancing Teacher Training

- **This includes Cumulative Development:** As 65% of all the teachers emphasized on further teacher training. This means that regular professional development will mostly enable integration of new and effective training techniques for teachers.
- **Workshops and Certifications:** Hold annual intensive training workshops using the English language to improve teachers' language skills and their application of interactive, student-centered approaches. Language Immersion Program: Tap into the "native" experience as an educator.
- **Immerse Teachers in activities:** Immersions may enable language experiences for teachers, especially in English-speaking countries; such exposure may advance their fluency level and acquaintance with current ELT methodologies..

5.2 Improving Teaching Materials and Curriculum

- **Curriculum Update:** 50% of the teachers that answered the survey supported an updated curriculum focused on communication skills and practical language use in sync with modern English language teaching approaches.
- **Updated Textbooks:** The nice and engaging textbooks must be supported by teachers and should emphasize real-life usage of the language instead of grammar and abstract concepts.
- **Concentrated Curriculum:** A concentrated curriculum, rather than a far-reaching one, would allow for more time to focus on speaking and listening activities, therefore enhancing students' verbal communications skills, since they would not have to waste time on reading and writing activities alone.

5.3 Reducing Class Sizes and Improving Student-Teacher Ratios

- **Smaller Classes:** : In order to improve customized education and boost student-teacher engagement, half of the instructors (50%) stressed the value of smaller classrooms, ideally with no more than 24 students in each.
- **Increased Staffing:** By hiring more teachers, the workload for existing educators would be lessened, allowing them to spend more time and focus on the academic development of each individual student.

5.4 Integrating More Technology in Classrooms

- **Smartboards and Digital Resources:** Noteworthy 44% of educators state that they require greater use of ICT in their classes. Things such as smartboards, language learning application software, and online resources must be incorporated into learning to make it lively.
- **Interactive Tools:** Access to technology allows heightened opportunity for more interactive lessons with increased input from the students enhancing the whole learning experience.

5.5 Expanding Opportunities for Speaking Practice

- **Increased Speaking Opportunities:** Emphasizing the need for expanded speaking opportunities in the curriculum through conversational activities, language clubs, and speaking exams, with a majority of teachers, i.e., 53%, supporting this move.
- **Language Clubs and Extracurriculars:** Building English-focused clubs and extracurricular activities greatly enhances student confidence and speaking ability in informal settings.
- **Project-Based Learning:** Projects, debates, and drama enhance the motivation for a real-life application of the English language out of the textbooks.

5.6 Extending Lesson Duration or School Year

- **Longer Lessons or Extended School Year:** 31% of teachers suggest increasing lesson duration or even extending the school year to provide more exposure to English and allow for more practice.

5.7 Introducing More Extracurricular Activities

- **Debates, Drama, and Language Clubs:** 36% of teachers suggest extracurricular activities like debates and drama to foster language use in real-world contexts. These activities promote critical thinking and creative expression in English.
- **Community Engagement:** Encouraging student participation in English activities outside of school, like volunteering, will further enhance their practical skills.

5.8 Encouraging Real-World Learning Opportunities

- **Internships and Project-Based Learning:** 37% of teachers recommend introducing real-world learning experiences such as internships or project-based learning to make English more applicable to students' daily lives.
- **Immersive Learning:** Facilitating opportunities for students to interact with native English speakers through exchange programs or online platforms is also essential.

5.9 Promoting Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving

- **Focus on Critical Thinking:** Based on feedback from 32% of participants, there is a strong preference for integrating critical thinking and problem-solving exercises into English instruction rather than relying on rote memorization.
- **Encourage Analytical Skills:** Encouraging students to engage in analytical, synthetic, and argumentative tasks in English can significantly improve both language proficiency and cognitive skills Vygotsky (1978).

5.10 Changing Teaching Approaches

- **Reconsidering Teaching Methodology:** A small fraction (1%) of educators suggested a complete overhaul of current teaching methodologies. Transitioning away from traditional lecture-based instruction toward more interactive, communicative, and engaging teaching techniques could be a beneficial step forward.

10. What improvements would help English teaching in Kurdistan? (Select all that apply)

100 responses

6. Conclusion

The present research throws light on the current scenario of English Language Teaching (ELT) in the Kurdistan region, including the major problems, deficiencies, and scopes for improvement. Literature analyzed and interview conducted with local teachers revealed considerable progress, but still it must address major issues regarding the quality of ELT.

Hence, this study demonstrates a dire need for increased allocation of state resources in curriculum development, teacher training, and modern teaching resources. For instance, teachers also emphasized the importance of greater speaking opportunities, integrated after-school activities, and real-life applications in their syllabus for enhancing student language skills. Besides, innovative teaching methods and technology should be brought into classrooms for a livelier and more engaging environment for both students and teachers to learn in.

This research also offered a few points that could solve the issues raised and create a more efficient, interesting system of English language education in Kurdistan. All of these are geared towards meeting the needs of teachers and students alike. They are improved teacher training, expanded extracurricular activities, and a focus on critical thinking. Governments, educational institutions, and ultimately instructors should join hands in making ELT better in Kurdistan. It is during this that the quality of English language instruction can be greatly raised as the concerns raised are addressed and the recommendations made put into action. This would ultimately equip students with the necessary tools to excel in a worldwide society.

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The main source of data collection of this paper is:

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